

Krishanarjuna Model of Learning Mathematics: Ecology of Learning Perspective

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ABSTRACT : This investigation examines students' engagement in a dialogue as a means of learning. In this study a self-dialogue communicational approach to cognition is adopted. Participants in this study are B.Ed. trainee student teachers. Students are encouraged to write down the dialogue that they have with themselves while they are thinking and trying to understand or create a proof. The results show the method of proving through writing a dialogue would be practical heuristic for involving students in the process of creating a mathematical proof. The reasonable flow of dialogue in this study indicates the expected change in the writer's mathematical discourse and his improvement in presenting a mathematical argument.

Keywords : Dialogue, Self-dialogue, Ecological approach , Mathematical discourse.

Introduction

The quality of mathematics instruction has an influence on learners' mathematics achievement. The insufficient nature of the mathematical knowledge of student teachers and in-service teachers, who are facilitators of learning and key figures in the transformation of mathematics teaching and learning, have serious implications for teacher training (Mapolelo, 1999). The main concern in education is to get a better understanding about the factors affecting students' performance and

the preparation of students for productive functioning in a highly demanding and continuously changing environment. In education, what is actually measured, is change in problem solving ability or change in conceptual understanding in a specific domain. There are evidences that mathematics students of the existing school system have lack of conceptual understanding. In order to facilitate conceptual understanding teachers themselves must possess profound mathematical knowledge. The content knowledge of teachers lack conceptual depth

and they are not capable of making conceptual knowledge accessible for learners (Hill, H.C., Rowan, B. & Ball, D.L. (2005)). Mathematical content knowledge consists of conceptual, procedural and conditional knowledge. Conceptual knowledge is knowledge rich in relationships and understanding and can be seen as a connected web of knowledge (Lester, F.K. & Kehle, P.E. (2003)). By definition, conceptual knowledge cannot be learned by rote, but by thoughtful, reflective mental activity. For better conceptualization of mathematical content we can help our students to engage in writing a mathematical dialogue. In mathematical discourse one can communicate mathematical concepts to other. So, mathematical discourse is a purposeful goal of teaching. The communicational approach is deeply rooted in Vygotskian theory, where priority is given to communicative public speech rather than inner private speech (Vygotsky, 1987). Therefore, better understanding of public discourse deepens our insight into a dialogue that one leads with oneself. In this paper we propose an ecological approach to learning processes.

Theoretical Framework

Considering the idea that thinking is a kind of communication that one has with oneself (Sfard, 2001), in this research, I encouraged students to write down the dialogue that they have with themselves while they were thinking to understand. Therefore, such dialogue should answer all the possible questions related to mathematical properties or arguments used to solve a mathematical problem. Writing down the dialogue may provide students an opportunity to reflect on their thinking process and to organize it in a convincing way. In this perspective, the

dialogue can be considered as an intermediate stage for conceptual learning.

While solving a problem there are two characters (friends) in the mind of every individual. One is all mighty LORD KRISHANA (Explorer) and another one is ARJUNA (WHYer). Krishana tries to solve (explore) the problem and Arjuna asks all possible questions. Writing dialogue would also cultivate the art of question posing, and after a while that would become a part of the culture of their mathematical thinking.

Methodology

Here we have introduced the notion of dialogue as a tool for involving B.Ed. Trainee student teachers in the process of creating a proof. By dialogue I mean a self-dialogue or a conversation that a person has with oneself while s/he is thinking. Therefore, writing the dialogue provides students with an opportunity to reflect on their thinking process, to correct the mistakes and fill the gaps in their argument, and to organize it in the form of a convincing mathematical discourse. It also provides a good source of students' discourses for educators and researchers. Indeed, it offers an opportunity for educators to examine students' arguments, and by posing more appropriate questions lead the students to refine and strengthen their arguments. To introduce the idea of writing proof through a dialogue the participants received a sample of a dialogue. The sample dialogue addresses a proposition. The main purpose of giving the sample dialogue is to show the students how many reasonable questions the proof of such simple statement might bring up. Hence, I wanted to encourage them to pose questions. I

believed writing dialogue would also cultivate the art of question posing, and after a while that would become a part of the culture of their mathematical thinking. The participants in this study were exposed to the task of creating dialogue for either proving a statement or expanding a given proof for number theory propositions.

Ecological Approach to the Learning of Number Theory

The following task was placed to B.Ed. Trainee teachers. Most of the participant teachers presented a reasonable dialogue by going through all the steps of the proof and addressing the key points of the given argument. In these dialogues, students presented convincing arguments by describing related vocabulary, choosing appropriate representations as mediators, manipulating them correctly by implementing mathematical routines, and interpreting the results by supporting them with appropriate endorsed narratives.

Task : Write a dialogue to prove the proposition.

Proposition : If p is a prime number and $p|ab$ then $p|a$ or $p|b$.

The following dialogue illustrates the performance of this category of students.

Krishana : Hey, Arjuna, I have a proposition for you, if p is a prime number and $p|ab$ then $p|a$ or $p|b$.

Arjuna : That is nice but what is a prime number?

Krishana : A prime number belongs to the set of whole numbers and has

only two divisors, 1 and the number itself p .

Arjuna : What does this symbol " $|$ " represent?

Krishana : The symbol " $|$ " symbol tells us that the number on the right (a, b , or ab) is divisible by the number on the left (p). Another way of putting $p|a$ for instance is that $p \times n = a$, where n is an element in the whole number set.

Arjuna : When you said " $p|a$ or $p|b$ " in your original proposition what exactly did you mean?

Krishana : The word "or" implies that if either or both of the criteria are met then the statement is true. Both $p|a$ and $p|b$ must be untrue in at least one case to disprove my original statement.

Arjuna : So have you proved your proposition yet?

Krishana : Not in the slightest. If I want to prove the proposition I will have to show you it is true in all cases.

Arjuna : I don't even understand one case let alone all of them, can you give me an example?

Krishana : Certainly, $5|50$ and $5|25$, although $5|2$ is untrue the proposition is still true because $5|25$. In this example $p = 5, a = 25, b = 2, ab = 50$.

Arjuna : Ok, that makes sense, the prime number 5 divides 50 and also divides 25 so your proposition is true in this case, but what about all cases like you mentioned earlier?

Krishana : well, for the general case we have to leave the proposition in its variable form with all of the p , a , b and ab , this way all of the possible situations are represented. So, if $p|ab$ then $p|a$ or $p|b$.

First, I will begin by writing the problem in another way.

If $p \times w = ab$, for some whole number w

Then $p \times y = a$ or $p \times z = b$, for some whole numbers y, z .

If a is written as a product of primes:

$a = p_1 \times p_2 \times p_3 \dots p_m$ and $b = q_1 \times q_2 \times q_3 \dots q_n$, where q is also prime.

$ab = p_1 \times p_2 \times p_3 \dots p_m \times q_1 \times q_2 \times q_3 \dots q_n$.

Arjuna : Hold on a minute, what does p_m represent?

Krishana : Numbers may have different numbers of prime factors, for example 60 can be decomposed into the primes $5 \times 3 \times 2 \times 2$. Here p_m is just a way of implying that there may be different numbers of primes and includes the entire prime decomposition of the number.

Arjuna : I understand. You can continue with what you were saying.

Krishana : Substituting from the above equation $p \times w = ab$,

$$p \times w = p_1 \times p_2 \times p_3 \dots p_m \times q_1 \times q_2 \times q_3 \dots q_n$$

The fundamental theorem of arithmetic sequence confirms that a composite number may be expressed as the product of primes in exactly one way, so our prime number p must be equal to one of the primes that compose the prime decomposition of ab . This can be demonstrated with an example:

$p|210$ the prime decomposition of 210 is $2 \times 3 \times 5 \times 7$, this also means that because 210 can only be expressed in one way the prime p must be a prime from the group 2, 3, 5 or 7 because they are the only primes that divide 210.

In the general case p must be equal to one of the primes between $p_1, p_2 \dots p_m$ or $q_1, q_2 \dots q_n$. Because p is equal to one of the primes that compose ab it also must help compose a or b or both.

Discussion and Conclusion

The benefit of writing dialogue is that it encourages students to „explain why and how to do instead of just doing. This is what Schoenfeld (1994) calls mathematical culture, where discourse, thinking things through, and convincing are important parts of students' engagement with mathematics. Having clear understanding of the mathematical vocabulary and using it appropriately is very important component of a mathematical discourse. The study demonstrates that explaining mathematical words is a common part of the dialogues. The majority of the students have posed questions

regarding the explanation and application of words or symbols and they answered them. That is to say, writing dialogue led them to make all the related definitions available and engaged them in the process of the proof.

In this dialogue the student began with clarification of the statement through describing related vocabulary and symbols, and providing a numerical example. The student, then by choosing appropriate representations, manipulating them correctly, interpreting and supporting the results by the Fundamental Theorem of Arithmetic drew a conclusion and created a convincing argument. The reasonable flow of this dialogue indicates the expected change in the writer's mathematical discourse and his improvement in presenting a mathematical argument. The results revealed that the main difficulty that students experienced in creating a proof is that they do not know how to communicate their idea mathematically.

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